

Numerical Analysis of Collatz Sequences Using Binary Representation

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Abstract

In this work, we explore the generation and analysis of Collatz sequences using binary representation to evaluate the length of the number at each iteration. Starting from randomly generated binary numbers using Python scripts, each transformation of the Collatz conjecture is studied to verify the reduction in the binary representation length, providing an empirical verification of the theoretical demonstration presented in a previous work. This numerical evaluation offers new insights into the dynamics of one of the most enigmatic conjectures in number theory, suggesting that representation in different bases can reveal structural properties that contribute to convergence to 1.

1 Introduction

The Collatz conjecture, one of the most fascinating unsolved problems in number theory, proposes that any positive integer iterated through the function $f(n)$ will eventually reach the value 1. Despite the simplicity of the rules—halving the number if even, or multiplying it by 3 and adding 1 if odd—the general proof for all numbers remains elusive. In a previous work (“A Simple Binary Analysis of the Collatz Conjecture”), we explored the analysis of the conjecture using binary representation, showing that reducing the binary length is key to convergence.

This paper aims to provide a numerical verification of the demonstration through computer simulations. Evaluating the binary length of randomly generated Collatz sequences allows us to analyze the reduction of the “binary energy” of each number until it reaches the minimum value of 1.

This project has been a collaborative effort, with Victor contributing significantly by developing and testing the computational code used to generate the graphs in this paper. His work not only ensured accurate visualization but

also supported the verification of theoretical predictions [1, for the theoretical foundation]. This collaboration reflects the importance of interdisciplinary and intergenerational approaches to mathematical research.

2 Sequence Generation Method

The method used to generate Collatz sequences starts with the random generation of binary numbers of a user-specified length. The function implemented in Python generates a random binary number, converts it to decimal, and proceeds to iterate the Collatz function. During each iteration, the length of the binary representation of the current number is recorded to empirically evaluate the reduction in length over time.

2.1 Code Used

The following Python code was used to generate the sequences and track their length at each step:

```
import random
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

def generate_random_binary_number(length):
    return ''.join(random.choice('01') for _ in range(length))

def collatz_length_analysis(binary_number):
    lengths = []
    current = int(binary_number, 2)
    while current != 1:
        lengths.append(len(bin(current)) - 2)
        if current % 2 == 0:
            current //= 2
        else:
            current = 3 * current + 1
    lengths.append(1)
    return lengths

var = int(input('please, input the length of the random binary number to analyse: '))
graphs = int(input('lastly, how many graphs would you like to see? '))

for i in range(graphs):
    random_binary_number = generate_random_binary_number(var)
    print(f"Initial random binary number {i+1}: {random_binary_number}")
    lengths = collatz_length_analysis(random_binary_number)
    plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
    plt.plot(range(len(lengths)), lengths, marker='o', linestyle='-', color='blue')
```

```
plt.title(f"Collatz: Binary Number Length at Each Step - Graph {i+1}", fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel("Steps", fontsize=12)
plt.ylabel("Binary Number Length", fontsize=12)
plt.grid(True)
plt.pause(5)
plt.close()
```

2.2 Code Description

The code uses two main functions:

- `generate_random_binary_number(length)`: generates a binary number of specified length, randomly choosing between 0 and 1.
- `collatz_length_analysis(binary_number)`: converts the binary number to decimal and applies the Collatz function, tracking the binary representation length at each step.

The code is structured so that the user can specify the length of the binary number and the number of graphs to generate. Each graph represents the evolution of the binary length for a specific sequence. The length analysis function is iterative: for each randomly generated binary number, the Collatz sequence is determined, and the length of the number is recorded and plotted for each step. This architecture allows exploration of the behavior of Collatz sequences for various initial values and visualizes the dynamics intuitively.

The sequences are analyzed in timescales of the order of seconds on a high-end notebook, making the simulation process practical for a variety of initial values.

The output is represented graphically, focusing on the variation in binary length during each iteration.

3 Results Analysis

The results of the simulations empirically confirm the hypothesis formulated in the previous paper: the binary length of a number progressively decreases until reaching the minimum value of 1, ensuring convergence. This behavior was observed for different initial lengths of binary numbers, and for each of them, the graph showed a gradual decrease in length.

3.1 Graph Interpretation

The obtained graphs show how the binary length decreases at each iteration, especially during division by 2, which corresponds to removing trailing bits. When the number is odd, the transformation $3n + 1$ produces an even number, which in turn leads to a reduction in length in subsequent iterations.

Additionally, it is observed that as the number of initial bits increases, the curve becomes progressively more "smooth," as expected due to the averaging

effect on a larger number of bits. However, oscillations along the curve are evident, indicating that while the general trend is toward a decrease, there are still significant local variations due to the intrinsic nature of the $3n + 1$ transformation. This behavior is consistent with theoretical expectations and offers an interesting perspective on the complexity of Collatz sequences.

Figure 1: The four graphs represent the binary length sequences for four different randomly generated binary numbers of increasing length (200, 400, 600, 800 bits). Each graph shows the variation in binary length during the steps of the Collatz sequence.

3.2 Significance of the Numerical Verification

This numerical verification is crucial to support the proposed theoretical demonstration. The empirical approach confirms the presence of recurring patterns in the reduction of binary length, supporting the argument that no infinite cycles other than the trivial cycle $1 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$ can exist. The systematic reduction in length suggests that binary representation is an effective tool for understanding the dynamics of the Collatz conjecture.

4 Conclusions

The study of Collatz sequences using binary representation offers an interesting perspective that can contribute to a better understanding of the iterative struc-

(a) 1000 bit

(b) 1000 bit

(c) 1000 bit

(d) 1000 bit

Figure 2: The four graphs represent the binary length sequences for four different randomly generated binary numbers of length 1000 bits. Each graph shows the variation in binary length during the steps of the Collatz sequence.

ture of the problem. The numerical verification performed confirmed that the binary length of the numbers involved in the iterations progressively decreases, thus strengthening the argument for convergence to 1.

This approach suggests that analyzing number theory problems in representations other than decimal can reveal fundamental structural properties. The next step will be to extend this method to similar problems or explore applications to other numerical bases to analyze whether analogous patterns emerge.

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References

- [1] Grosso, D. (2024). *A Simple Binary Analysis of the Collatz Conjecture*. University of Genoa.